

Testing Copula Hypothesis with Copula Entropy

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Abstract

Testing copula hypothesis is of fundamental importance in the applications of copula theory. In this paper we proposed a copula hypothesis testing with copula entropy. Since copula entropy is a unified theory in probability and therefore testing copula hypothesis based on it can be applied to any types of copula function. The test statistic is defined as the difference of copula entropy of copula hypothesis and true copula entropy. We propose the estimation method of the proposed statistic and two special cases for Gaussian copula hypothesis and Archimedean copula hypothesis. We test the effectiveness of the proposed method with simulation experiments.

Keywords: Copula Entropy; Copula; Hypothesis Test; Gaussian Copula; Archimedean Copula

1 Introduction

Evaluating the fitness of models to data is a common practice in scientific activities. Testing hypothesis is one of the fundamental problems in statistics and has wide applications in every branch of sciences.

Copula theory is about representing multivariate dependence with copula functions [1, 2]. As the core result of copula theory, Sklar's theorem [3] states that multivariate density function can be represented as a copula function with marginal functions as its inputs. There are many copula function families available for real applications, such as Gaussian copula, t Copula [4], Archimedean copula, Archimax copula [5], Sibuya Copula [6], among others.

Modeling with copula function is a widely used methods in many scientific fields [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12] and hence testing copula hypothesis is important in those practices [13]. Many research have been contributed to copula hypothesis testing, such as testing Gaussian copula hypothesis [14, 15], testing Archimedeanity [16, 17], testing symmetry of copula [18]. These work on testing copula hypothesis are mainly focusing on special types of copula function and a general method for any types of copula is needed. Kole, et al [19] suggest using Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and Anderson-Darling test to

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select copulas. Grønneberg and Hjort [20] proposed an AIC-like criteria for copula model selection, named Copula Information Criteria (CIC). Genest and Rémillard [21] proposed to use Cramér-von Mises test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for Goodness-of-fit testing of copula models.

Copula Entropy (CE) is a recently proposed theory in probability. It defined the concept of CE as a special kind of Shannon entropy with copula function [22]. Copula function represents the dependence relationship between random variables while CE measures such relationship in a unified way. Contrast to other dependence measures based on copula, such as Spearman's ρ and Kendall's τ , CE has many good properties, including non-negative, invariance to monotonic transformation, and equivalent to correlation matrix under Gaussianity. CE has been applied to hypothesis testing recently, including multivariate normality test [23], two-sample test [24], change point detection [25], and symmetry test [26].

In this paper, we proposed a copula hypothesis testing with copula entropy. It can be used for any types of copula hypothesis testing. The test statistic is defined as the difference of CE of copula hypothesis and true CE. We give the estimation method of the proposed statistic and two cases for Gaussian copula hypothesis and Archimidean copula hypotheses. We test the effectiveness of the proposed method with simulation experiments.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the basic theory of CE, Section 3 presents the proposed testing method, Section 4 gives the estimation method of the proposed statistic, simulation experiments will be presented in Section 5, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 Copula Entropy

With copula theory, Ma and Sun [22] defined the concept of Copula Entropy as follows:

Definition 1 (Copula Entropy). *Let \mathbf{X} be random variables with marginals \mathbf{u} and copula density function c . The CE of \mathbf{X} is defined as*

$$H_c(\mathbf{x}) = - \int_{\mathbf{u}} c(\mathbf{u}) \log c(\mathbf{u}) d\mathbf{u}. \quad (1)$$

They also proposed a non-parametric estimator of CE [22] comprising of two simple steps:

1. estimating empirical copula density function with rank statistic;
2. estimating the entropy of the estimated empirical copula density with the kNN entropy estimator[27].

If the copula density function c is given, the CE can also be estimated with the following way:

$$H_c(\mathbf{x}) = -E(\log c(\mathbf{u})). \quad (2)$$

3 Testing Copula Hypothesis

Given random variables $\mathbf{X} \in R^n$ and its samples \mathbf{X}_T associated with copula density function $c_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{u})$. Our goal is to test whether c belong to a hypothesis

$c(\mathbf{u})$, the null hypothesis of the problem is

$$H_0 : c_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{u}) = c(\mathbf{u}); \quad (3)$$

alternative hypothesis is

$$H_0 : c_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{u}) \neq c(\mathbf{u}). \quad (4)$$

We propose to test copula hypothesis with CE. The principle of testing is to compare the CE of the copula hypothesis with the true CE:

$$T_c(\mathbf{X}_T|c) = H_c(\mathbf{X}_T|c) - H_c(\mathbf{X}_T|c_{\mathbf{x}}), \quad (5)$$

The first term is the CE under the hypothesis of copula c and the second term is true CE. If H_0 is true, then T_c should be 0; otherwise, T_c should be large value.

Since CE is a unified theory for copula function, testing copula hypothesis based on CE can be used for any types of copula function. The only work needed is to select the copula family c .

4 Estimation

The statistic in (5) can be estimated as two part. The second term is true CE and therefore can be estimated directly from data with the nonparametric estimator of CE. The first term is the CE of copula hypothesis which can be estimated in the following 3 steps:

1. estimate empirical copula density $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$ from \mathbf{X}_T ;
2. estimate the parameters α of copula c with $\hat{\mathbf{u}}$;
3. calculate the CE of the copula hypothesis with the following equation:

$$H_c(\mathbf{X}_T|c) = -E(\log c(\hat{\mathbf{u}}; \alpha)). \quad (6)$$

In the first step, empirical copula density can be estimated with rank statistic and in the second step, the parameters α of copula density can be estimated with the likelihood method [2].

Here we give two special cases of estimating CE of copula hypothesis:

Gaussian Copula Gaussian copula density function can be written as the following [28, 29]:

$$c_n(\mathbf{u}) = |\Sigma_\rho|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \Phi(\mathbf{u})(\Sigma_\rho^{-1} - I)\Phi^T(\mathbf{u}) \right\}, \quad (7)$$

where Σ_ρ is correlation matrix, Φ is quantile normal function, and I is identity matrix.

So estimating CE of Gaussian copula hypothesis can be done as follows:

1. estimate Σ_ρ from \mathbf{X}_T ;
2. calculate the value of Gaussian copula with 7;
3. calculate CE of copula hypothesis with 6.

Archimedean Copula Gumbel copula, Frank copula, and Clayton copula are three main members of Archimedean copula family, and bivariate Gumbel copula density function is

$$c_g(\mathbf{u}) = \exp \left\{ - \left[\sum_{i=1}^2 (-\ln u_i)^\alpha \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \right\} \left[\left(\left[\sum_{i=1}^2 (-\ln u_i)^\alpha \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}-1} \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{(-\ln u_i)^\alpha}{u_i} \right) \right], \quad (8)$$

bivariate Frank copula density function is

$$c_f(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{\alpha(1 - e^{-\alpha})e^{-\alpha(u_1+u_2)}}{\{1 - e^{-\alpha} - (1 - e^{-\alpha u_1})(1 - e^{-\alpha u_2})\}^2}, \quad (9)$$

and bivariate Clayton copula density function is

$$c_c(\mathbf{u}) = (\alpha + 1)(u_1 u_2)^{-\alpha-1}(u_1^{-\alpha} + u_2^{-\alpha} + 1)^{-2}, \quad (10)$$

where α is the parameter of Gumbel copula.

So estimating CE of Archimedean copula hypothesis can be done as follows:

1. estimate α with the likelihood method [2];
2. calculate the value of Archimedean copula with (8), (9) or (10);
3. calculate CE of Gumbel copula with (6).

5 Simulations

We test the proposed method with two simulation experiments ¹. The first experiment simulate bivariate Gaussian copula with correlation coefficient ρ range from 0.1 to 0.9 by the step 0.1. The second experiment simulate bivariate Gumbel, Frank, and Clayton copula with the parameter α changing from 2 to 10 under the margins being standard normal distribution and exponential distribution. All the sample size of simulations is 300.

We applied the above testing method of Gaussian copula hypothesis and Archimedean copula hypotheses to simulated data and derived four estimated statistics from each sample set.

The experimental results is shown in Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4. It can be learned that in the first simulation experiment, the estimated statistics of Gaussian copula hypothesis is smaller than those of Archimedean copula hypotheses and that in the second simulation experiment, the estimated statistics of Gumbel, Frank, or Clayton copula hypothesis is smaller than those of Gaussian copula hypothesis and the other Archimedean copulas. These mean that Gaussian copula hypothesis is true and Gumbel, Frank, or Clayton copula hypothesis is true in two experiments respectively.

The R package `copula` [30] was used for Archimedean copula. The R package `mvtnorm` [31] was used for simulating Gaussian distribution. The R package `copent` [32] was used as the implementation of CE estimator.

¹The code is available at <https://github.com/majianthu/tch>

Figure 1: Results of Gaussian copula hypothesis simulation experiments.

Figure 2: Results of Gumbel copula hypothesis simulation experiments.

Figure 3: Results of Frank copula hypothesis simulation experiments.

Figure 4: Results of Clayton copula hypothesis simulation experiments.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we proposed a copula hypothesis testing with copula entropy. The test statistic is defined. The estimation method of the proposed statistic is proposed and two special cases of tests for Gaussian copula hypothesis and Archimedean copula hypothesis are given. The effectiveness of the proposed method is verified with simulation experiments.

References

- [1] Roger B Nelsen. *An introduction to copulas*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2007.
- [2] Harry Joe. *Dependence modeling with copulas*. CRC press, 2014.
- [3] Abe Sklar. Fonctions de repartition an dimensions et leurs marges. *Publications de l'Institut de statistique de l'Université de Paris*, 8:229–231, 1959.
- [4] Stefano Demarta and Alexander J. Mcneil. The t Copula and Related Copulas. *International Statistical Review*, 73(1):111 – 129, 2005.
- [5] Radko Mesiar and Vladimír Jágr. d-dimensional dependence functions and archimax copulas. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 228:78–87, 2013. Special issue on AGOP 2011 and EUSFLAT/LFA 2011.
- [6] Marius Hofert and Frédéric Vrins. Sibuya copulas. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 114:318–337, 2013.
- [7] Valdo Durrleman, Ashkan Nikeghbali, and Thierry Roncalli. Which copula is the right one? *Available at SSRN 1032545*, 2000.
- [8] Christian Genest, Bruno Rémillard, and David Beaudoin. Goodness-of-fit tests for copulas: A review and a power study. *Insurance: Mathematics and Economics*, 44(2):199–213, 2009.
- [9] Andrew J. Patton. A review of copula models for economic time series. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 110:4–18, 2012. Special Issue on Copula Modeling and Dependence.
- [10] Yanqin Fan and Andrew J. Patton. Copulas in econometrics. *Annual Review of Economics*, 6(Volume 6, 2014):179–200, 2014.
- [11] Faranak Tootoonchi, Mojtaba Sadegh, Jan Olaf Haerter, Olle Råty, Thomas Grabs, and Claudia Teutschbein. Copulas for hydroclimatic analysis: A practice-oriented overview. *WIREs Water*, 9(2):e1579, 2022.
- [12] Mohammad Nazeri Tahroudi, Rasoul Mirabbasi, Aliheidar Nasrolahi, and Seyed Yagoub Karimi. A review of copula-based approach for water resources time series. *Water Harvesting Research*, 6(1):131–144, 2023.
- [13] Daniel Berg. Copula goodness-of-fit testing: an overview and power comparison. *Copulae and Multivariate Probability Distributions in Finance*, pages 67–93, 2013.

- [14] Yannick Malevergne and Didier Sornette. Testing the Gaussian copula hypothesis for financial assets dependences. *Quantitative Finance*, 3(4):231–250, 2003.
- [15] Dante Amengual and Enrique Sentana. Is a normal copula the right copula? *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 38(2):350–366, 2020.
- [16] Piotr Jaworski. Testing archimedeanity. In Christian Borgelt, Gil González-Rodríguez, Wolfgang Trutschnig, María Asunción Lubiano, María Ángeles Gil, Przemysław Grzegorzewski, and Olgierd Hryniewicz, editors, *Combining Soft Computing and Statistical Methods in Data Analysis*, pages 353–360, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2010. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [17] Axel Bücher, Holger Dette, and Stanislav Volgushev. A test for archimedeanity in bivariate copula models. *Journal of Multivariate Analysis*, 110:121–132, 2012. Special Issue on Copula Modeling and Dependence.
- [18] Christian Genest, Johanna Nešlehová, and Jean-François Quessy. Tests of symmetry for bivariate copulas. *Annals of the Institute of Statistical Mathematics*, 64(4):811–834, August 2012.
- [19] Erik Kole, Kees Koedijk, and Marno Verbeek. Selecting copulas for risk management. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 31(8):2405–2423, 2007.
- [20] Steffen Grønneberg and Nils Lid Hjort. The copula information criteria. *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics*, 41(2):436–459, 2014.
- [21] Christian Genest and Bruno Rémillard. Validity of the parametric bootstrap for goodness-of-fit testing in semiparametric models. *Annales de l’Institut Henri Poincaré, Probabilités et Statistiques*, 44(6):1096 – 1127, 2008.
- [22] Jian Ma and Zengqi Sun. Mutual information is copula entropy. *Tsinghua Science & Technology*, 16(1):51–54, 2011.
- [23] Jian Ma. Multivariate normality test with copula entropy. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2206.05956*, 2022.
- [24] Jian Ma. Two-sample test with copula entropy. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.07247*, 2023.
- [25] Jian Ma. Change point detection with copula entropy based two-sample test. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.07892*, 2024.
- [26] Jian Ma. Testing symmetry with copula entropy based two-sample test. *ChinaXiv preprint ChinaXiv:202505.00167*, 2025.
- [27] Alexander Kraskov, Harald Stögbauer, and Peter Grassberger. Estimating mutual information. *Physical Review E*, 69(6):066138, 2004.
- [28] Peter Xue-Kun Song. Multivariate dispersion models generated from gaussian copula. *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics*, 27(2):305–320, 2000.
- [29] Philipp Arbenz. Bayesian copulae distributions, with application to operational risk management—some comments. *Methodology and Computing in Applied Probability*, 15(1):105–108, March 2013.

- [30] Jun Yan. Enjoy the joy of copulas: With a package copula. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 21(4):1–21, 2007.
- [31] Alan Genz and Frank Bretz. *Computation of Multivariate Normal and t Probabilities*. Lecture Notes in Statistics. Springer-Verlag, Heidelberg, 2009.
- [32] Jian Ma. copent: Estimating copula entropy and transfer entropy in R. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.14025*, 2021.